

THE EFFECTS OF THE FIRST DONALD J. TRUMP ADMINISTRATION'S MAXIMUM PRESSURE POLICIES ON THE ENERGY POLITICAL ECONOMY OF THE ISLAMIC REPUBLIC OF IRAN

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Abstract

The maximum pressure policies of the first Donald Trump administration against the Islamic Republic of Iran, especially after the unilateral withdrawal from the JCPOA in 2018, had profound effects on the political economy of Iranian energy. This study examines the impact of these policies on Iran's oil, gas, and renewable energy industries. The findings show that the sanctions imposed since 2018 have caused profound structural changes in the political economy of Iranian energy. In the oil sector, sanctions have led to an 85% reduction in oil revenues (from \$119 billion in 2017 to \$17 billion in 2022) and a sharp drop in exports from 2.5 million barrels per day to around 0.5 million barrels per day. The gas industry has also faced serious challenges in developing joint fields and exports, with gas exports to Iraq and Turkey falling by around 60%. In contrast, the renewable energy sector has witnessed relative growth. The installed capacity of renewable energy has increased from 300 MW in 2017 to over 1,000 MW in 2023, and the private sector's share in this area has reached 40%. Iran's adaptive strategies have included developing regional cooperation, increasing technological self-reliance, and diversifying export markets. However, fundamental challenges such as aging infrastructure, the need for large-scale investment, and Technological limitations remain.

Keywords: US Sanctions, Iran's Energy Economy, Trump Administration, Oil and Gas, Renewable Energy.

INTRODUCTION

The first administration of Donald Trump (2017-2021) imposed unprecedented sanctions on key sectors of the economy, especially energy, by adopting a policy of "maximum pressure" against Iran. The aim of these policies was to reduce Iran's oil revenues and weaken its economic power. This research examines the impact of these sanctions on three main sectors of Iran's energy: oil, gas, and alternative energies.

Theoretical Framework

The political economy of energy examines the interaction between politics, economics, and energy markets. As a geopolitical tool, US sanctions had a direct impact on Iran's oil revenues and energy security by limiting Iran's access to global markets. To analyze the effects of the Trump administration's maximum pressure policies on Iran's energy economy, we need a combination of international relations, political economy, and energy theories. This theoretical framework encompasses three levels of analysis: 1. The international system level (structural analysis); Aggressive realism theory (Mearsheimer): Explaining the maximalist behavior of the

United States in imposing sanctions. 2. Nation-state level (agency analysis) Political economy of resistance: A local framework for examining Iran's strategies in the face of sanctions. 3. Energy industry level (policy analysis) Energy transition theory (Gahl): Examining the developments in the renewable energy sector under sanctions. By combining different approaches, this theoretical framework allows for a multi-level analysis of the effects of sanctions. The main focus is on the interaction between external coercion (sanctions) and internal responses (adaptation and resistance) in the Iranian energy system. This approach helps to understand the dynamics of the political economy of Iranian energy under sanctions.

Problem statement

Over the past two decades, the nuclear issue has had an impact on Iranian political and economic affairs more than any other issue. In July 2015, the Islamic Republic of Iran and the P5+1 group reached an agreement on the Joint Comprehensive Plan of Action (JCPOA), under which sanctions imposed on the Islamic Republic of Iran by the United Nations Security Council and the United States, and in some cases by the European Union, on the nuclear issue were suspended and lifted in exchange for Iran's moderation of its nuclear activities over a specified period of time. In addition to its critics within Iran, the agreement was criticized by the Saudi Kingdom and the Zionist regime in the Middle East. In the United States, as a key party to the agreement for Iran, the JCPOA became an issue in political competitions and the election campaign for the 2016 presidential election.

During the election campaign, Donald Trump criticized his Democratic rival, Hillary Clinton, and her supporters among the country's political authorities for accepting the JCPOA and receiving billions of dollars from it for the Islamic Republic of Iran. Donald Trump won the presidential election in November 2016 and, as promised, after his victory on May 8, 2018, he officially withdrew the United States from the JCPOA and reimposed secondary sanctions against the Islamic Republic of Iran that had been suspended following the JCPOA. In addition, by the end of Trump's presidency, the United States had imposed sanctions on the Islamic Republic of Iran on various issues, including declaring the Revolutionary Guard Corps a terrorist organization. These measures are part of what Trump calls the maximum pressure policy against the Islamic Republic of Iran. In this study, we seek to answer the question of what have been the effects of the maximum pressure policies of the first Donald J. Trump administration on the political and energy economy of the Islamic Republic of Iran?

Background

The Trump administration's maximum pressure policies against Iran (2017-2021), especially after withdrawing from the JCPOA, had a wide-ranging impact on the political economy of Iran's energy. Numerous studies in the fields of international relations, energy economics, and sanctions have examined this issue. This section reviews the most important domestic and foreign research related to this issue. Salehipour (2012) concluded in his book *US Sanctions and the Iranian Economy* that Trump's sanctions reduced Iran's oil exports by 80 percent and severely affected the country's foreign exchange earnings. Brindan (2020) concluded in an article titled *US Sanctions and Iran's Green Energy Transformation* that sanctions provided an

incentive for the development of solar energy in Iran, but the lack of advanced technology limited the progress of this sector. Previous studies show that sanctions during the Trump era had a detrimental impact on Iran's oil and gas industry, but at the same time, they provided an incentive for the development of renewable energies.

Research Method: The present research method is descriptive-analytical. The method of collecting information related to the research literature is a library method based on card-taking, including various books and articles and domestic and foreign publications. In order to obtain as much information as possible about the research topic and to understand it more accurately, and in order to determine research goals and optimally use the results and findings of previous research conducted by researchers on the subject in question, various existing resources in the libraries of educational centers and universities (domestic and foreign books, articles, publications, magazines, and theses related to the subject) are examined through the card-taking tool. And in some cases, electronic and internet archives are also used." And finally, the collected information will be written in a descriptive-analytical manner.

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

The Concept of Sanctions

Sanctions in international law and politics are a set of measures of a coercive nature that aim to force states, international actors, or non-compliant individuals to comply with the norms of international law or to follow the will and policy of the institution issuing the sanctions. Technically, this term is used for both military and non-military actions, but it is mainly used for non-military actions. The motivation for imposing sanctions may be a response to a violation of a norm or to prevent its violation, but in fact, the motivation for imposing sanctions can be to achieve a foreign policy goal or to obtain some privileges from the sanctioned country. In today's global politics, sanctions as a foreign policy tool have attracted the attention of powerful countries, because imposing sanctions can provide these great powers with an opportunity to try to change the behavior of a state or an actor without resorting to force. change international law. Sanctions can be imposed unilaterally, multilaterally, or based on international resolutions. Non-international sanctions require a UN resolution, but in multilateral sanctions, several countries usually agree to impose sanctions on another country. In unilateral sanctions, one country acts alone against another country. The latter two cases do not require a Security Council resolution, and the agreement of the countries provides the basis for sanctions. From the perspective of international law, there are three different approaches to unilateral sanctions by one country against another:

- A. The first approach is that the imposition of these sanctions is permitted based on the principle of state sovereignty. In other words, since states can act freely in regulating their foreign relations with others, each state has the political right to sever or establish relations with another state. The same relationship also exists in economic matters; therefore, based on this approach, states can put another state under economic pressure to advance their political goals.

- B. In the second approach, direct economic warfare by one state against another is permitted, and its harmful effects on third parties should be minimized. The main focus of economic sanctions is on the target state or states, and therefore these sanctions should have the least effects on other states.
- C. The third approach is the legal prohibition approach. This school does not allow secondary sanctions, but also primary sanctions. This group believes that no type of sanctions should be imposed against states in the modern international legal system, because the negative consequences of sanctions far outweigh their positive consequences. In the final review of the above theoretical approach and comparison with the practices of countries, we conclude that the sanctions measures of countries against each other are expanding in many cases despite legal prohibitions. One of the most important unilateral sanctions measures in recent years has been the sanctions imposed by the United States on countries such as Iran, Iraq and Libya.

A brief classification of the types of sanctions is given below: A: Non-economic sanctions include: travel sanctions, air sanctions, military sanctions and diplomatic sanctions. B) Economic sanctions are the most common type of sanctions. There are two main types of economic sanctions.

- A. Trade sanctions: Trade sanctions restrict imports to and exports from the sanctioned country. This restriction may be comprehensive, such as the Iraq embargo, or it may be selective, restricting only some specific goods. Comprehensive sanctions were imposed on Iraq in August and September 1991 to force it to withdraw from Kuwait. In April 1992, comprehensive sanctions were imposed on that country again to implement Security Council Resolution 687 following Operation Desert Storm. Comprehensive sanctions were imposed on Yugoslavia (1991-1996), Serbia and Montenegro (1992-1996), and Haiti (1993).
- B. Financial sanctions: Financial sanctions are closely related to economic sanctions, but their focus is on prohibiting the flow of money and financial resources into or out of the sanctioned country. Financial sanctions, as discussed in the Interlaken Process, can include freezing government assets, restricting access to financial markets and credit, restricting international financial exchange, and restricting sales and trade abroad. Financial sanctions are part of all UN sanctions against targeted countries.

Economic sanctions are used by many governments as a foreign policy tool. Economic sanctions are usually imposed by a larger country on a smaller country for one of two reasons: either the latter is perceived as a threat to the former's security or the latter is not treating its citizens fairly. Sanctions may be used as a coercive measure to achieve specific policy goals related to trade or human rights abuses. Economic sanctions are used as an alternative to war to achieve desired results. Imposing sanctions on an opposing country also has some effect on the economy of the sanctioning country. If import restrictions are imposed, consumers in the sanctioning country may have limited choices for goods. If export restrictions are imposed or if sanctions prevent companies in the sanctioning country from doing business with the target country, the sanctioning country may lose markets and investment opportunities to competing

countries. Critics of sanctions, including Belgian jurist Marc Bossuet, argue that in non-democratic governments, the extent of their impact on political events is debatable, since such governments, by definition, do not respond strongly to popular will.

Trump's Maximum Pressure Policy Against Iran

After announcing its withdrawal from the JCPOA, the Trump administration's most important action in advancing the hybrid war against the Islamic Republic of Iran was the imposition of severe economic sanctions. From the perspective of Trump administration officials, the purpose of imposing these sanctions was to cut off Iran's sources of income and, in this way, prevent the Islamic Republic of Iran from pursuing regional policies and a missile program. The Trump administration considered economic sanctions to be the most effective lever of pressure to confront what it called the Islamic Republic of Iran's "destructive behavior." The effectiveness of economic sanctions and their consequences on the behavior of the Islamic Republic of Iran formed the foundation of the Trump administration's maximum pressure policy against the Islamic Republic of Iran. For this reason, by announcing its withdrawal from the JCPOA, Trump imposed sanctions against the Islamic Republic of Iran's oil exports, petrochemical industries, steel industries, etc. within a specific time frame. Although the embargo on oil exports, as the Islamic Republic of Iran's main source of revenue, was an important part of the Trump administration's sanctions regime, various institutions suggested that Iran's financial system be sanctioned as a solidifying element of the new round of sanctions. The Trump administration's ultimate goal in imposing economic sanctions was to bring the Islamic Republic of Iran back to the negotiating table and reach a comprehensive agreement with the country. However, Trump administration advisers believed that before any negotiations could take place, the Islamic Republic of Iran must be deprived of its sources of revenue. According to hardline members of the Trump administration, "bad groups" need money to carry out destructive behaviors; therefore, in order to change Iran's behavior and prevent its "subversive" actions in the region and globally, the country's sources of revenue must be cut off.

The Foundation for Defense of Democracies, one of the most important institutions supporting Trump's maximum pressure policy against the Islamic Republic of Iran, considered economic sanctions to be the most important tool to force Iran's leaders to return to the negotiating table and, in its proposals to the Trump administration, called for maintaining economic sanctions even during negotiations. In sum, the imposition of sanctions was the economic aspect of the Trump administration's combined war against the Islamic Republic of Iran. The important point in implementing these sanctions was that, unlike the Obama administration, the Trump administration did not consider lifting sanctions as a path to return to the negotiating table, but rather that sanctions were part of the Trump administration's strategy to force Iran to choose the negotiating table. Many critics of the Trump administration doubted its outcome, and many others described it as a failed strategy.

Impact of Sanctions on the Iranian Oil Industry

The program to "reduce Iran's oil exports to zero" was another goal of the Trump administration, which was defined within the framework of the maximum pressure strategy

and implemented in the form of the second wave of sanctions. Since Iran's economy is dependent on oil revenues, the sanctions have dealt a severe blow to the country's economy. In April 2018, Iran's oil exports were over 2.5 million barrels per day, but after the sanctions were imposed, this figure dropped to 400,000 to 500,000 barrels per day. Trump's sanctions on Iran's oil industry included a ban on buying oil from Iran, sanctions on oil companies, and banking restrictions. These measures led to:

- A sharp decline in Iranian oil exports: Iran's oil exports fell from around 2.5 million barrels per day in 2017 to less than 300,000 barrels per day in 2020.
- Financial and technical problems in the upstream oil sector: International companies such as Total and Royal Dutch Shell withdrew from Iranian projects.
- An increase in oil sales through informal means: Iran resorted to methods such as transporting oil to China and Syria via silent ships.

Impact of Sanctions on Iran's Gas Industry

During the JCPOA, Iran signed contracts with foreign companies, the largest of which was the contract to develop Phase 11 of South Pars with the French company Total and the Chinese company CNPC. According to this contract, gas production from this phase of South Pars was to reach 56 million cubic meters per day. However, after the US withdrew from the JCPOA, Total withdrew from the contract and the development of Phase 11 was entrusted to CNPC. However, Chinese companies, especially during the previous round of sanctions, have not left a good track record in Iranian oil and gas fields.

For example, several Chinese companies worked in the Azadegan oil field and delayed the development of this field without any valid reason and were eventually expelled from this field by Iran. Also, Chinese companies that have interests in the US may not be willing to invest in Iran. Sanctions have been one of the main reasons for Iran's failure in its gas export policy. However, there are other reasons besides external obstacles to achieving this goal, including "the long process of reaching an agreement on major decisions in Iran" and "the prevailing view of domestic gas consumption."

Therefore, even without considering the recent sanctions imposed by the Trump administration against Iran, there was little hope before that for attracting foreign capital and technology to develop the oil industry, especially Iran's gas. Private foreign companies have the financial resources to create momentum and transformation in Iran's oil industry, and Iran's oil and gas industry also has great attractions and potential for foreign companies.

However, attracting foreign investors requires an appropriate legal framework and an efficient and rapid decision-making process, as well as political stability. In addition, achieving such a goal requires improving foreign relations and resolving international disputes, and improving relations, especially with neighboring countries.

Without attracting foreign capital, Iran has little chance of developing and producing from its oil and gas fields and is unlikely to be able to pursue its gas export plans.

Iran has the world's second-largest gas reserves, but sanctions have also hampered the sector's development:

- Restrictions on gas field development: Joint projects such as South Pars have been delayed.
- Reduced technological cooperation: Companies such as Russia's Gazprom have limited cooperation with Iran due to US pressure.
- Increased domestic gas consumption: As oil exports have declined, Iran has turned to using more gas to generate electricity.

Impact of sanctions on alternative and renewable energies

After withdrawing from the JCPOA, the Trump administration-imposed sanctions on Iran's iron, steel, aluminum, and copper industries, which account for about 10 percent of the country's export revenue. Trump's goal was to cut off funding for its nuclear program, ballistic missile development, and support for proxies. The timing of these sanctions coincided with the anniversary of the JCPOA withdrawal, reflecting Trump's decision-making style: symbolic timing and strategic targeting. In addition to imposing economic pressure, his administration's goal was to send a clear geopolitical message.

The sanctions imposed on the iron and steel industries had a significant impact on the Iranian economy. Export volumes declined, and Iran faced serious challenges in accessing international markets. The decline in revenues strained the government budget and limited Iran's ability to finance regional activities. However, Iran was able to adapt and use its power components. Exports to countries such as China continued, and Iran used informal networks to circumvent the sanctions. Domestic consumption of metals increased, and dependence on exports decreased. Although the sanctions created economic pressure, they failed to cripple the industry or achieve the Trump administration's broader goals.

Iran, relying on its strategic tools, resisted the sanctions and found ways to reduce economic pressure. In response, Iran strengthened economic relations with countries such as China and Russia, exploited smuggling networks, and supported domestic production. These measures helped to alleviate some of the economic pressure; although challenges arising from the sanctions remained. With the Trump administration set to take office in January 2025, it is expected that the administration will continue to exert economic pressure on Iran. This strategy will likely include revising existing sanctions and targeting new sectors. One likely area of focus is the renewable energy sector.

Iran has made significant progress in investing in renewable energy, such as solar and wind, to diversify its energy sector and reduce its dependence on hydrocarbons. Sanctioning this sector could hinder Iran's progress in energy diversification and economic resilience. Targeting renewable energy is consistent with the Trump administration's strategy to limit Iran's economic adjustment to sanctions. Companies such as SANA have made significant progress in developing solar and wind projects, making this sector an attractive target for economic pressure. Sanctioning renewable energy serves two purposes: to suppress this emerging sector

and to exacerbate Iran's energy imbalances, as the country relies heavily on oil and gas exports for revenue. Disrupting renewable energy could make Iran more dependent on its hydrocarbon sector, which is subject to intense scrutiny and sanctions. So far, the United States has not imposed direct sanctions on Iran's renewable energy sector. However, broader sanctions imposed on Iran's economy and energy sector have indirectly affected the development of renewable energy. For example, financial sanctions and trade restrictions have limited Iran's access to foreign technology and investment in renewable energy. Iran has demonstrated that it has the tools and power to influence regional dynamics, including military capabilities. Intensifying sanctions could lead to increased tensions in the Middle East. The region is already facing instability, with the conflict between Israel and Hezbollah and the unrest in Syria. These developments suggest that further economic pressure on Iran could fuel regional conflicts; therefore, the United States should balance its actions to prevent a large-scale conflict while maintaining pressure on Iran. This delicate balance highlights the complexity of the administration's decision-making process in the face of Iran's actions and maintaining regional stability.

Overall, the Trump administration's potential focus on sanctions on Iran's renewable energy could have significant consequences for the country's economic and environmental development. The move could slow Iran's progress on clean energy, increase its dependence on fossil fuels, and undermine global efforts to combat climate change. The shadow of sanctions on renewable energy represents a new phase of economic pressures that could upset regional balances and highlight the need for innovative diplomatic solutions to reduce tensions and prevent further conflict. Although the sanctions have created many challenges, they have also provided an impetus for clean energy development:

- Growth in domestic production of solar and wind energy equipment: Iran has turned to domestic solar panel manufacturing due to import restrictions.
- Increasing the share of renewable energy in the energy portfolio: The installed capacity of renewable energy increased from 300 MW in 2017 to about 1,000 MW in 2021.
- Reducing dependence on oil revenues: The Iranian government adopted policies to diversify energy sources.

CONCLUSION

Trump's maximum pressure policy against Iran, although it strained Iran's energy economy in the short term, strengthened its self-reliance and alternative energy development strategies in the long term. However, declining oil revenues and technological constraints left fundamental challenges for Iran's energy industry. Although these policies dealt significant blows to Iran's energy industry, they did not lead to Iran's complete isolation from global energy markets. By adopting adaptive strategies, Iran was able to reduce the pressure of sanctions to some extent, although it incurred significant economic costs. The future of Iran's energy industry will depend on the extent to which it succeeds in diversifying its economy, developing domestic technology, and improving international relations.

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